

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART I. A NEW SYNTHESIS OF CADALENE

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Cadalene and *apo*-cadalene have been synthesised by new and simpler procedures starting from *p*-cymene.

The succinic anhydride method ranks as an important synthetic tool amongst the various methods which are being employed in building up polycyclic hydrocarbons. Haworth and his co-workers used it extensively in the phenanthrene series (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1125, 1784, 2248, 2717, 2720; 1934, 454). The method has also been used in the synthetic investigations on carcinogenic hydrocarbons (Cook *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1933, 398; 1934, 428; 1935, 767; 1938, 505; Adelson and Bogert, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 1776, *et seq.*). The method furnishes sometimes a very convenient route to many alkyl naphthalenes which have been synthesised by rather complicated procedures (Heilbron and Wilkinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2537; Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, 15, 140; 1936, 19, 370, *et seq.*).

Cadalene, the important dehydrogenation product of some sesquiterpenes, was identified by Ruzicka and his co-workers as 1:6-dimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene both by analytical and synthetic methods (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, **5**, 345, 369). The hydrocarbon has also been synthesised by various other workers (Barnett and Cook, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 22; Bardhan and Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1935, 476; Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 588; Dutta, *ibid.*, 1941, **18**, 233). All these schemes involve steps from 7 to 11. The succinic anhydride synthesis is much simpler and is outlined above.*

In order to establish the conditions, succinic anhydride itself was employed in the first instance, 1-methyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (*apo-cadalene*) was thus synthesised. A number of independent syntheses of this is on record (Ruzicka and Migazzini, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, **5**, 714; Rapson and Short, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 128; Barnett and Cook, *ibid.*, 1933, 22).

p-Cymene is condensed with succinic anhydride or pyrotartaric anhydride in nitrobenzene solution in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to give the corresponding keto-acids (II, X). Since the substitution in the *p*-cymene ring nearly always occurs in the position 2 (*e.g.* acetylation, Claus, *Ber.*, 1886, **19**, 232), and also because methylsuccinic anhydride is known to react in such a way that the carboxyl group, furthest removed from the methyl, attaches to the aryl nucleus invariably (Klobb, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1900, *iii*, **23**, 511; Oppenheim, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 4227; Haworth and Bolam, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2248) the condensation products are expected to be of the desired structure. But in order to place the structures beyond doubt, the acids have been synthesised by straight forward methods. *p*-Cymene is acetylated to give 2-acetyl-*p*-cymene (VII) (Allen, "Organic Syntheses," XIV, p. 1). If this condensation is carried out in nitrobenzene instead of carbon disulphide, the yields are very much improved. A 70% yield is readily obtained instead of the 50-55% yields reported (*loc. cit.*). A change of solvents in such a condensation is known to alter the orientation sometimes (St. Pfau and Ofner, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1926, **9**, 669; Fieser, Holmes and Newman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1055; Chopin, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1924, *iv*, **35**, 610). This product on oxidation with potassium hypobromite yields *p*-cymene-2-carboxylic acid, m.p. 71-72° (*cf.* Bogert and Tuttle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 1349). 2-Acetyl-*p*-cymene is brominated with one mole of bromine in dry ether to give the corresponding ω -bromo compound (VIII), the crude bromo compound is then condensed with the proper malonic ester to give (IX) or (XV). The esters, thus obtained, are hydrolysed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide and then decarboxylated at 180°-200° to give the keto-acids indistinguishable from the direct Friedel-Craft's condensation products.

The keto-acids are reduced by amalgamated zinc and hydrochloric acid, an immiscible solvent being employed (Martin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1438). The *p*-cymyl-2-acids (III and XI), so prepared, are obtained in good yields. In the case of γ -(*p*-cymoyl-2)-propionic acid, besides the normal reduction product (III), another product

* When this work had been completed and a preliminary note communicated to the *Science & Culture* in December 1946, a new synthesis of cadalene by Johnson and Jones appeared (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 792). Their synthesis is simpler than the previous syntheses but the present scheme still remains the simplest.

of m.p. 210-211° has been isolated which is insoluble in hot 20% aqueous potash. Huang-Minlon (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 2487) during the Clemmensen's reduction (Martin's procedure) of β -(*p*-phenoxybenzoyl)-propionic acid isolated a high melting byproduct for which he proposed the structure of the pinacol-dilactone. The product is insoluble in cold alkali. Similarly during the reduction of β -benzoylpropionic acid, a solid (m.p. 254°) has been isolated to which Fieser has given a similar structure ("Organic Syntheses", Vol. XV, p. 64). But since our product is insoluble in hot 20% aqueous potash, it is highly improbable that it is a lactone. The substance is under investigation.

The cyclisations of these acids to the corresponding tetralones (IV, XII) have been accomplished by the Friedel-Crafts intramolecular condensation of the acid chlorides. Ruzicka (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, **5**, 369) has reported the 2:5-dimethyl-8-isopropyl-tetralone-1 (XII) as a liquid, whereas our product soon crystallises out after distillation (m.p. 50-51°).

5-Methyl-8-isopropyltetralone-1 (IV) is reduced to the secondary alcohol (V) by sodium and absolute alcohol. But this reduction is carried out better by sodium in moist benzene. The 2:5-dimethyl-8-isopropyltetralone-1 (XII) is reduced in this way. Dimolecular reduction does not take place to any appreciable extent (cf. Ruzicka, *oc. cit.*)

The alcohol (V) is heated with selenium first at about 180°, when the evolution of the dehydration water practically ceases. The temperature is then raised to 280° and the dehydrogenation effected. 1-Methyl-4-isopropylmaphthalene (VI) is isolated and characterised in the usual manner.

The alcohol (XIII), however, is first dehydrated with formic acid and then dehydrogenated with selenium to give cadalene (XIV).

EXPERIMENTAL

Syntheses of Keto-acids

(1) *2-Acetyl-p-cymene* (VII).—Anhydrous aluminium chloride (45 g., 1 mol.) was added in two lots to dry nitrobenzene (50 c.c.) placed in a three-necked flask and mechanically stirred. When the aluminium chloride had dissolved, the flask was cooled in an ice-salt mixture to 0°, when the aluminium chloride-nitrobenzene complex separated out. A mixture of *p*-cymene (43.7 g., 50.1 c.c., 1 mol.) and acetyl chloride (27.7 g., 25 c.c., 1 mol.) was then introduced in the reaction mixture dropwise during 45 minutes; the temperature was not allowed to rise beyond 10°. The flask was surrounded with more ice and the reaction mixture was left overnight (15 hours). Next day the reaction mixture, full of colourless crystalline addition product, was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. The oil was extracted with ether, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the ether removed. The residue was carefully fractionated from a 250 c.c. modified Claisen's flask, when 40 g. (70%) of the product were obtained, b.p. 118-20°/9 mm.

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared in the usual manner (sulphuric acid method) as yellow needles, crystallising in stars from petrol ether (75°-90°) containing 5% benzene, m.p. 137.5-138.5°. (Found: N, 15.58. C₁₄H₂₀O₄N₄ requires N, 15.72 per cent).

Acetylcymene (2.0 g. in 5 c.c. dioxane) was oxidised with potassium hypobromite and the 2-methyl-5-isopropylbenzoic acid was isolated in the usual manner and crystallised thrice from dilute acetic acid in long, white needles, m.p. 71-72° (Bogert and Tuttle, *loc. cit.* give m.p. 71.7°).

(ii) *Keto-acids* (II, X).—2-Acetyl-*p*-cymene (10 g., 1 mol.) in dry ether (10 c.c., dry carbon tetrachloride is less favourable) was chilled in ice. A trace of anhydrous aluminium chloride was added and then bromine (3 c.c., 1 mol.) was added slowly in 1 c.c. portions, the second addition being made only when the first had been decolorised. Decolorisation was very rapid, though there was some initial lag. When the reaction was complete, ether and hydrogen bromide were removed immediately under suction in a very thin current of dry air. The syrupy liquid residue was then left in a vacuum desiccator overnight.

Sodium (1.27 g., 1 mol.) was powdered under 10 c.c. of dry xylene. The xylene was decanted off, the sodium washed with 10 c.c. portions of dry benzene twice and then immediately covered with dry benzene (20 c.c.). The appropriate malonic ester (1.1 mol.; diethyl malonate, 10.0 g.; methyl diethylmalonate, 10.5 g.) was added, the sodium salt was formed instantaneously appearing as a white gelatinous mass. When the initial reaction had subsided, the mixture was heated on the water-bath for 2 hours to complete the formation of the sodium salt and then cooled in ice.

The above ω -bromo-ketone was taken up in dry benzene (15 c.c.) and added all at once to the sodium salt of the malonic ester. The reaction started at room temperature; a lot of heat was generated, the complex began to dissolve with the precipitation of sodium bromide. When the reaction had slackened down (15 min.) the mixture was heated on the water-bath till all the sodium salt had dissolved (6 hours).

The reaction mixture was cooled, agitated with 50 c.c. of water and just acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and then steam-distilled to remove the solvent and any unreacted malonic ester. The syrupy, reddish oil that remained was taken up in ether, the solution washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated. The residue was hydrolysed by refluxing for 5 hours with 15% alcoholic sodium hydroxide (100 c.c.). The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water, made just neutral with hydrochloric acid taking care that no acid precipitated out and then it was boiled with norit and filtered. The cooled solution was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when the dibasic acid precipitated out as an oil which soon crystallised. The crystals were filtered off and heated in an oil-bath at 180-200° for half-an-hour to effect decarboxylation. The residue was crystallised from a suitable solvent.

β -(*p*-Cymoyl-2)-propionic acid (II) was obtained as colourless, prismatic needles (petrol ether 75°-90°), m.p. 76-77° and β -(*p*-cymoyl-2)- α -methylpropionic acid (X), as white plates (petrol ether & benzene, 2:1), m.p. 118-119°.

Syntheses of the Hydrocarbons

An Improved Method for the Preparation of Methylsuccinic Anhydride.—Several methods for the preparation of methylsuccinic acid are known (Higginbotham and Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 51; "Organic Syntheses", XXVI, p. 54; Verkade and Hartman, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1932, 52, 947; Meyer and Stamm, *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 1426;

Adkins and Wojcik, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 2424; Bischoff and Guthzeit, *Ber.*, 1881, **14**, 614; Bone and Sprankling, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, **78**, 853). The following modification of Bone and Sprankling's method (*loc. cit.*) gave the best results.

Sodium (23 g., 1 atom) was powdered under xylene (150 c.c.) in a three-necked flask (2 litre) fitted with a stirrer (mercury sealed), a condenser carrying a guard tube and a dropping funnel. The xylene was decanted off and replaced by dry toluene (1 litre). The stirrer was started and ethyl malonate (1 mol., 160 g.) was added rapidly (15 min.). The reaction was rapid and when it had slowed down (half-an-hour), the mixture was refluxed with stirring for 3 hours and then cooled to room temperature. α -Bromopropionic ester (181 g., 1 mol.) was added dropwise to the rapidly stirred jelly of the sodium salt (2 hours). The reaction mixture was left overnight and then refluxed for 6 hours. The mixture was diluted with water, the toluene layer separated, washed with water, dilute hydrochloric acid (twice) and then with water. The wet toluene solution was distilled in vacuum to remove the toluene and the residual oily liquid was heated in an oil-bath at 170° under 100 to 120 mm. pressure to remove the unreacted components. The ester was next refluxed with 500 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid till the oily layer had disappeared (7-10 hours). The mixture was then poured in an evaporating basin and the hydrochloric acid removed on the water-bath; the residue was cautiously treated with small amounts of concentrated nitric acid (twice) to oxidise the impurities and then evaporated with water till all the nitric acid had been expelled. The syrup was cooled to room temperature with stirring when it had solidified completely. Yield of the crude acid of m.p. 100-105° was 105 g. to 120 g. (80-90% of theory).

Acetyl chloride (150 c.c.) was added slowly to the crude acid (105 g.) placed in a flask carrying a reflux condenser with a guard tube. After the initial reaction had subsided, the mixture was refluxed for 2 hours on a water-bath and then fractionated in vacuum. The anhydride boiled at 118-120°/7 mm. as a colourless, oily liquid, yield 75 g. (83.3%). A small amount (0.2 g.) was evaporated to dryness with water (5 c.c.) to give pure methylsuccinic acid, m.p. 112°.

(i) *Condensation of Succinic and Methylsuccinic Anhydrides with p-Cymene: Formation of β -(p-Cymoyl-2)-propionic Acid (II) and β -(p-Cymoyl-2-) α -methylpropionic Acid (X).*—*p*-Cymene (purified by sulphuric acid treatment, 35 g., 41 c.c., 1.1 mol.), acid anhydride (1 mol., methylsuccinic anhydride, 28 g. or succinic anhydride, 24.4 g.) and freshly distilled nitrobenzene (150 c.c.) were placed in a 2-litre, three-necked flask carrying a mercury-sealed stirrer, a thermometer and an exit tube (CaCl₂ guard tube); the third neck was used for adding the anhydrous aluminium chloride. The mixture was stirred vigorously and cooled to -5° in a salt-ice mixture bath. Anhydrous aluminium chloride (74 g., 2.2 mol.) was added during 1½ hours in 4 lots; during these additions the temperature was not allowed to go beyond 10°. The stirring was then continued in the ice-bath for 3 hours more. The ice-bath was replenished, stirring stopped and the reaction mixture left overnight (12 hours). Next day the mixture was stirred for 2 hours at room temperature (22°). The reaction mixture had an appearance of a clear orange-red syrup which was transferred to a litre round-bottom flask, chilled in an ice-salt mixture and the complex decomposed with 200 g. of crushed ice followed by 60 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The mixture was allowed to stand for an

hour and then steam-distilled to remove practically all the nitrobenzene. The residue was poured into a beaker (1 litre), cooled and some ice added; the oil soon solidified on slight scratching to a nearly white mass, which was filtered, washed with water and dissolved in aqueous sodium carbonate solution (water, 250 c.c., sodium carbonate, 40 g.). The solution was boiled to remove the last traces of nitrobenzene, treated with norit (if necessary) and filtered to remove some inorganic material. The filtrate and the washings were combined, cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid (Congo red). The solid acid was removed by filtration, washed several times and then dried in a vacuum desiccator.

β-(*p*-Cymoyl-2-)-propionic Acid (II).—Yield of the crude product was 85%; it crystallised from petrol ether (75°–90°) in stout prisms and prismatic needles, m.p. 76–77°, yield 40 g. (70%). The product is very soluble in alcohol, benzene and ethyl acetate. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid to give a deep yellow solution and melts to a red liquid. (Found: C, 71.13. H, 7.9. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 71.79; H, 7.69 per cent).

β-(*p*-Cymoyl-2-)-*α*-methylpropionic Acid (X).—Yield of the crude product was 80.5%; it crystallised from 2 parts of a mixture of benzene (1 part) and petrol ether (75°–90°, 2 parts) in plates and prisms crystallising in stars, m.p. 118–119°, yield 36.5 g. (60%). (Found: C, 72.81; H, 8.34. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 72.58; H, 8.06 per cent).

A longer time of reaction, or a higher temperature increased the yield of the crude product, but decreased that of the pure compound.

(ii) *Clemmensen's Reduction of (II) and (X): Formation of γ*-(*p*-Cymyl-2-) butyric Acid (III) and *γ*-(*p*-Cymyl-2-)-*α*-methylbutyric Acid (XI).—The pure acid (15 g.) was reduced with zinc amalgam (from 37 g. zinc wool, 3.7 g. of mercuric chloride, 2 c.c. of conc. hydrochloric acid and 55 c.c. of water) and hydrochloric acid (conc., 65 c.c. and water, 27 c.c.) with the addition of toluene (37 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.) by refluxing for 34 hours in an oil-bath at 120°–140°. After every 6 hours, 15 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (conc.) were added. The reaction mixture was cooled, the toluene layer separated, washed with water and the wet solution distilled under reduced pressure to remove the toluene. The residue was distilled from a modified Claisen's flask in vacuum.

γ-(*p*-Cymyl-2-)-butyric Acid (III) was obtained as a thick colourless oil, b.p. 170–75°/3 mm., yield 12.5 g. (86%). Ruzicka (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 714) gives b.p. 195–200°/12 mm.

The small residue left after distilling (III) was boiled with water, cooled and the solid collected by filtration. On crystallisation from glacial acetic acid it formed small silky needles, m.p. 210–11°, yield 1 g.

γ-(*p*-Cymyl-2-)-*α*-methylbutyric Acid (XI) was obtained as a thick colourless liquid, b.p. 176–78°/3 mm., yield 11 to 13.5 g. (80–95.7%). Ruzicka (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 369) gives b.p. 200–201°/11 mm.

(iii) *Ring-closure of (III) and (XI): Formation of 5-Methyl-8-isopropyltetralone-1 (IV) and 2:5-Dimethyl-8-isopropyltetralone-1 (XII)*.—Phosphorus pentachloride (9.8 g., 1.1 mol.) was placed in a distillation flask (100 c.c., side tube plugged) and covered with 15 c.c. of dry benzene. The acid (1 mol., 10 g.), dissolved in dry benzene (20 c.c.), was added in 2 lots to PCl_5 and the acid chloride was prepared in the usual manner. The benzene and the $POCl_3$ were removed by distillation under vacuum at a temperature not exceeding 90°; the discolorisation of the acid chloride was avoided.

Anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.2 g., 1.1 mol.) was placed in a 100 c.c. conical flask carrying a calcium chloride guard tube, and immediately covered with ligroin (free from unsaturation and aromatics, b.p. 75°-90°, 20 c.c.) and cooled in an ice-salt bath at -10°. The acid chloride was taken up in thiophen-free benzene (20 c.c.) and also cooled in an ice-bath. The thoroughly cooled acid chloride solution was added all at once to the aluminium chloride-ligroin mixture and swirled. On warming to room temperature (24°) the reaction started with vigorous evolution of hydrochloric acid gas. The reaction with the chloride of (*p*-cymyl-2-)-butyric acid (III) was more rapid and started at a lower temperature. When the vigour of the reaction had subsided, the mixture was just warmed on a water-bath at 50° and taken out, and the reaction allowed to proceed as such; this was repeated (3-4 times) till all the aluminium chloride had just disappeared. The mixture was dark black in colour. This was poured on to ice (100 g.) and hydrochloric acid (conc., 15 c.c.) and kept for half-an-hour with occasional stirring. Ether (about 25 c.c.) was added and the red solvent layer removed, washed successively with dilute hydrochloric acid, water, dilute caustic soda (twice) and water, and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue, left after removal of the solvents under diminished pressure, was distilled from a 20 c.c. modified Claisen's flask.

5-Methyl-8-isopropyltetralone (IV) was obtained as a colourless, mobile oil, b.p. 163°-66°/11 mm., yield 70%. 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone (sulphuric acid method) gave bright red, flat needles (benzene & petrol), m.p. 198.5-199.5°. (Found: N, 14.51. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.65 per cent).

2:5-Dimethyl-8-isopropyltetralone (XII) was obtained as a colourless, very slightly viscous liquid, b.p. 141-42°/3 mm., yield 8.0 g. (87%). The liquid crystallised out completely after a day as stout, large prisms (petrol ether, 40°-60°), m.p. 50-51°. (Found: C, 82.46; H, 9.87. $C_{15}H_{20}O$ requires C, 83.33; H, 10.18 per cent). 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone, prepared as above, gave bright red, lustrous, needle-like plates, crystallising in stars (petrol & benzene), m.p. 212.5-213.5°. (Found: N, 14.09. $C_{21}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.14 per cent).

(iv) 1-Methyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (apo-Cadalene) (VI).—The ketone (IV, 6 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (60 c.c.), was reduced in the usual manner with sodium (4 g.).

The crude reduction product (5.7 g.) was dehydrogenated by heating with selenium (4 g.) in a metal-bath at 180°-200° for 1 hour till all the dehydration water had been expelled, and then heating at 260°-280° for 17 hours, when the evolution of hydrogen selenide had ceased completely. The cooled reaction mixture was extracted with ether, the ether evaporated and the residual oil distilled over sodium in vacuum, when 5 g. of a colourless mobile oil, b.p. 162°-175°/18 mm. were obtained. The hydrocarbon was purified by regeneration from the picrate and then had b.p. 145-48°/11 mm. Picrate, orange needles from alcohol, m.p. 99-100° Ruzicka and Migazzni (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 99-100°.

(v) Cadalene (XIV).—The crystalline ketone (XII, 4.5 g.) in benzene (40 c.c.) was placed in a three-necked flask carrying a reflux condenser, a dropping funnel and a mercury-sealed stirrer. Sodium (8 g., cut in very thin slices) was added to the

benzene solution and 20 c.c. of water were added at a very slow rate to the rapidly stirred solution, till all the sodium had reacted (1½ hours). The reaction mixture was diluted with water, the benzene layer removed and washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and then twice with water. The wet solution was distilled to remove the benzene, the last traces being removed in vacuum, when 4 g. of a slightly coloured, mobile liquid were left. The crude carbinol was dehydrated with 90% formic acid (6 g.) for 2 hours at 80°, and the unsaturated hydrocarbon isolated in the usual manner as a colourless, mobile liquid, b.p. 132°-140°/9 mm., yield 2.8 g. (73%). The compound was unsaturated to bromine in chloroform.

To the dihydrocadalene (2.8 g.) selenium (3 g.) was added and the mixture heated first at 280°-290° for 10 hours and finally at 310°-320° for 15 hours, when no more hydrogen selenide was evolved. The cadalene was isolated with ether in the usual manner and distilled over sodium, b.p. 132-140°/4.5 mm., yield 1.5 g. (55%). *Picrate*: orange-yellow needle (alcohol), m.p. 115-16°, mixed m.p. with an authentic sample (natural source) remained undepressed. Ruzicka (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 114-15°.

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